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VISIGOTHIC SCRIPT + THE DIGIPAL SOFTWARE

Report of WP2 Digital Analysis of BL 11695

Project ViGOTHIC:

Objectives:

- (i) Apply and evaluate computer-assisted techniques (DigiPal) to the study of Visigothic script;
- (ii) Determine the viability and benefits of computerised semi-automated analysis;
- (iii) Establish a point of reference for computerised analysis of Visigothic script codices by providing accurate graphic foundations to foster historical research.

Foreseen benefits of the application of the software:

- (i) It will allow me to determine the specific corpus of the project and leave it open for future research; I could then add other manuscripts from Silos combining digital surrogates from different archives.
- (ii) It will make easier to conduct research with several manuscripts at the same time, and, once the project grows, will speed up the work with larger amount of sources.
- (iii) Since DigiPal is designed to describe handwriting, I will be able to mark the images with detailed descriptions or notes for future research.
- (iv) It will help to reconstruct the hand of a scribe, from one or several sources, the script used in a specific production centre (Silos) and in a particular period of time (late 11th c.); the cultural context of the British Library Beatus and its coeval manuscripts.
- (v) Since DigiPal is a semi-automatic tool – the researcher selects the relevant features to build the digital library – it will allow me to determine and share the method needed for graphic analysis of Visigothic script sources.
- (vi) It will structure my research from the beginning, simplifying the comprehension of the research process carried out; the advances done conducting research will be easy to show and follow.
- (vii) And, other scholars could take advantage of my research, promoting collaborative work.

INITIAL COMMENTS "all these small pieces are not comprehensible; they are out of their context!" It might look that way if one looks at the library of features alone, but once selecting a feature or, vice versa, going to a manuscript and looking to what has been added in notes (marking) by the researcher, the "big picture" appears. A specific folio with the marks of the cuttings made. Searching by features, references to in which manuscript or part of a manuscript that feature was used. Searching by hands, it will be possible to match the same hand coming from different sources and build up its whole career through manuscripts and throughout the years.

(i) Apply and evaluate computer-assisted techniques (DigiPal) to the study of Visigothic script through the codex example BL 11695;

The first step was to conduct the manual palaeographical analysis of the codex [BL Add. MS 11695](#) (The Silos Apocalypse). In the process, I identified a total of five scribes/hands (plus one more with a minor intervention) working on the copy of the manuscript. I established which parts of the codex were copied by whom, and studied the relationship between scribes in the process of copy. I also determined two master illuminators draw the miniatures for which the codex is famous and their relationship with the scribes within the codex. My conclusions are significant: the codex was thought to have been copied by just two scribes who gave their names in the colophon of the codex, plus only one illuminator. By identifying two scribes and one illuminator more, I obtained significant information to reconstruct the written production of the monastery in which the codex BL Add. MS 11695 was copied.

The second step was the contextualisation of the information obtained in the previous step. For that purpose, I analysed all manuscript production that has been thought to have been a product of the same monastery: a total of 19 codices. After careful consideration, I determined that only seven of these codices, besides the codex example BL Add. MS 11695, could have indeed been produced in that centre: a *Commicus* (BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2171), Isidore's *Etymologiae* (BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2169, fols. 25 et sqq.), a *Passionarium* (BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2179), Cassian's *Collationes* (BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2170), a *Breviarium* (BL, Add. MS 30848), a *Homiliarium* (BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2176), and another *Homiliarium* (BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2177). Moreover, I identified the same hands/scribes and illuminators of BL Add. MS 11695 in several of these codices (Hand4 in BL, Add. MS 30848; Hand2 in BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2176; Hand4 in BnF, nouv. acq. lat. 2177) what allowed me to conclude the scriptorium was organised and of considerable importance. I also established the period in which it was active and conducted research on the cultural – political and liturgical – context that led to its decline.

The third step was to carry out the digital palaeographical analysis of the codex by applying the software developed by the team DigiPal. The process implied: to collect and upload the images of the codex example to the platform, to specify its characteristics, to classify each image as a particular part of the codex, to link images to the correspondent stints of each scribe, and to annotate them gathering representative graphic examples of each hand. The process of analysis was, altogether by adding this tool, much quicker and more objective, being not only easier and faster to reach the same conclusions as with the traditional manual analysis but also to provide significant graphic evidence in support of each phase of the process and each conclusion. The software also made easier to establish comparisons among hands/scribes by using the “lightbox” app where the user can alter the image for this particular purpose.

(ii) Determine the viability and benefits of computerised semi-automated analysis (DigiPal);

	<i>Pros</i>	<i>Cons</i>
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ It requires initial training to get used to work with the programme and to understand how it works. Someone from one of the DigiPal teams needs to dedicate around 3h to teach a new user. The DigiPal team offers training sessions under request for small groups of researchers/students. ○ Once the initial training is done, it is easy to work with and understand the software. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Once the initial training is done, the user might need further assistance (see “support” below). Constant communication with the DH developers is an asset. Notwithstanding this, there are several pages (glossary; project rationale) in the DigiPal main website (www.DigiPal.eu) explaining how the software works and why it was designed like it has, which greatly help new users to get familiar with the program.
Workability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ It is easy to communicate with the software; to input data and understand the output. ○ The software is mostly designed to be used online (external hosting) for it incorporates many options to share the process of palaeographical analysis directly, but it can also be used offline (self-hosting). In self-hosting the software – aka. installing the program and working with the images hosted on your computer – the main website (www.DigiPal.eu) provides a how-to guide. The software is openly available at http://github.com/kcl-ddh/digipal, where those users who opt for the self-hosted version can download it and access to updates. ○ The software allows for a group of researchers to work together in a specific DigiPal team. The program registers the contributions of each member of the team individually, permitting: to retain intellectual property of the work done by each researcher; to establish work-packages for each member of the team and revise progression, and to quickly solve mistakes a user might have done for the administrator can delete all changes made by one particular user. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If the user opts for the external hosting option to work with the program, he or she depends on the DH team to set up the site (for example as in my case with VisigothicPal) and to keep it working, solving any problems that might arise. ○ To have a version of DigiPal, as VisigothicPal, under external hosting is expensive; external funding is needed to cover the costs of the software developers and the hosting space. ○ If the user opts for the self-hosting option, he or she might require further assistance (see “support” below).

Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The team of developers of DigiPal are very helpful and capable when the user has any problems in working with the software. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The user needs to be in regular contact with the software developers to grant the correct implementation and functioning of the program.
Copyright	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software is freely available to any user at http://github.com/kcl-ddh/digipal. ○ Although the software is open access, the images that each user/research group adds to it might not be so. DigiPal has foreseen this and solved it by incorporating an option to select the copyright restrictions of each image (available both in self-hosted and externally-hosted; Mezzanine>Image>Media permissions). Therefore, those images that are not OA will not be viewed by external users (they will have access to the notes based on the image), only by the members of the research team, allowing to work with the images in collaboration without infringing copyright restrictions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ None
Corpus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ It is essential to define a corpus of sources with which to work. Each source will correspond to an image or group of images that will be uploaded to DigiPal by the users (team members; Mezzanine>Image>Images). The fact that it is required to upload all the material allows the get a better insight of the corpus selected and of the work to be done with it. It helps to identify sources that were not initially included in the corpus, but that could be required for its contextualisation. The software allows changes in the initial corpus at any time. ○ The software allows detailed classification of each source (Mezzanine>Item). There are fields to fill in for identifying the type of source (Mezzanine>Item>Historical item), repository, shelfmark, item and its parts (Mezzanine>Item>Current item and Item parts), date, place, provenance, language, hand/scribes, etc. Thus, each source is linked to its cultural 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Each image uploaded to the software needs to be correctly classified, identifying its type, repository, shelfmark, etc. Whereas this classification is relatively easy to work with for codices and parts of codices, it is a bit more complicated for charters. This is not a problem of the software per se, but still, it seems is much more complicated than needed. Also, to begin the analysis of a specific source, a name needs to be defined for its scribe. This name can be changed as the work develops but it might be difficult to identify the same scribe/hand in different sources. The initial traditional analysis is required before adding the information into DigiPal. [this will need to be revised for further work on VisigothicPal]

	<p>context easing searches for sources with similar data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software permits to digitally reconstruct manuscripts that have been severed since, when describing the item, several parts of the same can be linked and will be so during the descriptive analysis. 	
Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software allows adding transcriptions and translation of the sources added. Not tested for this project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Not known.
Terminology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software works with a predefined terminology based on the definition of ontographs, characters, allographs, components, and component features, that needs to be adapted to each type of corpus and defined by the team (Mezzanine>Symbol and Descriptor). It allows a correct classification of the nuances of each hand/scribe. ○ The fact that a specific terminology needs to be set from the beginning gives consistency to the research work and clarity in expressing results. It structures the research process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Each research team needs to arrive at a consensus in defining the terminology to be used and be consistent in using it. Since palaeography does not have a specific terminology and each scholar uses his or her own, it might cause problems to standardise one specific list of terms. [this will need to be revised for further work on VisigothicPal]
Annotation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The user does the annotations of each source, not the software itself what results in a more refined analysis that dismisses not relevant information (instead of having lists of all letterforms, abbreviations, etc. the user only works with those that are relevant). ○ Following the terminology defined by the research team, the user can annotate and easily fill in all the information required for the correct classification of each graphic sample (character type, character, allograph, components, and component features). ○ When marking an annotation, the annotation is not severed from the source. Therefore, each note made can be easily contextualised, which could not be done without using the software. ○ Besides making annotations directly on the source, there are optional fields for adding more detailed notes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ When working with a written sample that has text in several directions, the image cannot be rotated to allow annotation in all areas of text. ○ Being the user who decides which graphic information is relevant to annotate, it might be that he or she misses sensitive data that would be, working with an automatic software, saved. However, the software gives the opportunity to go back to analysing a source (new information can be added at any time as the specialist increases his or her expertise), and if everything was annotated, the significant bits might go unnoticed.

	on palaeographical analysis or historical significance of the annotations/source/hand.	
Visualisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software incorporates a “lightbox” tool through which alter the original image(s) which is particularly useful for example to see faded text and to superpose images to check similarities in hands/scribes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ None
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software is designed for a group of researchers to work with the same corpus at the same time. This does not only mean several people can access but that the amount of work each does is identified and recorded. Also, the software incorporates several fields through the process of analysis to be used as internal working notes to communicate with the members of the team. ○ The group of researchers within the same project is not closed; new users can join through the duration of the project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ None
Retrieval of information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software has a robust system for advanced searches that allows retrieving any information added following very specific criteria. These searches can, for example, provide all graphic evidence of a specific hand/scribe or a particular place or historical period together even when the data comes from different sources. At the same time, it opens new research questions since the information retrieved might not be what the user was expecting, thus requiring further research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ None
Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The software allows for each user to share each part of the process of analysis through links. ○ The software adapted to each research team is presented as a functional web page, easing the dissemination of results through posts, news, twitter feed, etc. ○ Any person interested in accessing the research conducted can do so through the site. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ None
Impact	I believe the software could be a great tool for teaching as well as for developing further impact (organising exhibits for the general public, hosting interviews...).	

<p>Comparison with other software</p>	<p>DigiPal is a semi-automatic tool. The software does not make the annotations - it does not tell the specialist what is important - the user does. It was designed to help the palaeographer rather than to substitute him/her. The fact that there is no algorithm to mark the relevant features automatically (as, for example, with the projects Humanis and Oriflammes by Dominique Stutzmann) is positive. Instead of presenting all the different variations of all the letterforms, signs, etc. creating a library of hundreds of features without a context, by using DigiPal only the relevant features will make it to the digital library. It is hard to work, trying to set some conclusions, with hundreds of <i>a</i>'s, <i>b</i>'s..., easier with only relevant examples.</p>
<p>Results</p>	<p>DigiPal allows to work with a bigger corpus quicker, efficiently, and adding much more objective detailed graphic information. It also improves comparisons among sources, a fundamental part of the palaeographical research. Besides, DigiPal classifies all the relevant information the user considers important providing information that helps solve specific research questions while at the same time creating new ones.</p>

(iii) Establish a point of reference for computerised analysis of Visigothic script codices by providing accurate graphic foundations to foster historical research.

In order to fulfil the third step of the project (the digital analysis of the codex example BL Add. MS 11695) I, in collaboration with the DigiPal team, developed the site VisigothicPal. The software DigiPal is integrated within it. Once the platform site+software was running, it was a requirement to set a specific terminology for the correct description of Visigothic script sources, and to provide graphic samples for each of the terms used. This terminology sets the basis for continuing using the software as well as for describing Visigothic script in the traditional manual palaeographical analysis, and constitutes the foundation from which to continue studying the script, its evolution, and historical context.

The terminology, focused in the minuscule or book-hand typological variant of the script, is based on the definition of character types, characters, allographs, components, and components' features.

- 'Character', similar to sign, refers more or less to a set of letters in the abstract sense also including punctuation and abbreviations. So the letters *a, b, c*, etc. are characters, as also the full stop, question mark, accent mark, etc. Note that nothing is said about what the character looks like, so *d* and *ð* are the same character.
- 'Allograph' is a recognised variant form of the same character in an abstract way (e.g. Visigothic and Caroline *a*). A form of a given letter common to a group of people (e.g. Roman *a* vs. italic *a*).
- 'Component' is a unit which, alone or in combination, makes up a character or allograph. Where the component in two different characters/allographs is produced in the same way then it should have the same name; e.g. both *b* and *p* have component 'bow', whereas *a* and *æ* have a 'lobe'.
- 'Feature' refers to a descriptive label which can be applied to a component (e.g. 'long', 'short', 'wedged').

Bearing in mind this terminology, the minuscule Visigothic script is described as follows (the table compares the terms used with those of other research projects based on DigiPal):

CHARACTER TYPE: LETTER

<i>characters</i>	<i>allographs</i>		components (essential elements)			
			VisigothicPal	DigiPal1 /Peter blog	DigiPal2	MoA
a	Visigothic a		curve + upright	-	-	-
a	Caroline a		stem + bow	bowl/bow/lobe + back	back + headstroke + lobe	stem + lobe + headstroke
a	Uppercase a		-	-	-	-
b	b		stem + bow	ascender + bowl	ascender + bowl	shaft + lobe
b	Uppercase b		-	-	-	-

c	c		curve + head-stroke	hook + bowl (lower curve?)	hook + lower curve	stem + headstroke
c	Uppercase c		-	-	-	-
d	Visigothic d		stem + bow	bowl + ascender/ba	ascender + bowl	shaft + lobe
d	Uncial d		stem + bow	-	stem + bowl	shaft + lobe
d	Uppercase d		-	-	-	-
e	e		curve + bow (head-stroke?) + cross-stroke	eye (hook + tongue) + bowl (lower curve?)	eye + lower curve + tongue	stem + headstroke + tongue
e	e caudata		curve + bow + cross-stroke + virgule	-	-	-
e	Open e		curve + curve + cross-stroke	-	-	-
e	Uppercase e		-	-	-	-
f	f		stem + head-stroke + cross-stroke	hook + tongue + descender/	downstroke + hook + tongue	shaft + headstroke + crossbar
f	Uppercase f		-	-	-	-
g	Visigothic g		curve + down-stroke + head-stroke	-	-	-
g	Caroline g		bow + down-stroke	mid-component or bowl +	-	stem + lobe + tail + finishing stroke
g	Uppercase g		-	-	-	-
h	h		stem + arch	ascender + arch (upper curve + down-stroke/minimum)	ascender + arch	shaft + limb + arch
h	Uppercase h		-	-	-	-
i	i		upright	minim	minim	stem

i	Tall i		upright	-	-	-
i	Long i		head-stroke + down-stroke	-	-	-
i	Uppercase i		-	-	-	-
k	k		stem + bow + cross-stroke	ascender + upper branch + lower branch	ascender + downstroke + lower branch + upper branch	shaft + branch + lobe + upper branch
k	Uppercase k		-	-	-	-
l	l		upright	ascender	ascender	shaft
l	Uppercase l		-	-	-	-
m	m		stem + arch + arch	minim + middle arch + final arch	minim + mid- arch + arch	limbs (first, middle, final) + arches
m	Uppercase m		-	-	-	-
n	n		stem + arch	minim + arch	minim + arch	limbs + arch
n	Uppercase n		-	-	-	-
o	o		bow	bowl	bowl	left lobe + right lobe
o	Uppercase o		-	-	-	-
p	p		stem + bow	bowl + descender	bowl + descender	shaft + lobe
p	Uppercase p		-	-	-	-
q	q		curve + head- stroke + down- stroke / bow + down-stroke	bowl + descender	bowl + descender	shaft + lobe
q	Uppercase q		-	-	-	-

r	r		upright + head-stroke	hook + minim or descender + arch	hook + minim	stem + headstroke
r	Round r		upright + bottom-stroke	-	-	stem + basestroke
r	Uppercase r		-	-	-	-
s	s		upright + head-stroke	-	downstroke + hook	shaft + headstroke
s	Uppercase s		-	-	-	-
t	t		curve + curve + head-stroke	-	-	-
t	Inverted beta t		curve + curve + stem	-	-	-
t	Cursive t		oblique + bottom-stroke	-	-	-
t	Caroline t		curve + head-stroke + upright	(top stroke + bowl/lower curve?)	(lower curve + top stroke)	(stem + headstroke)
t	Uppercase t		-	-	-	-
u	u		upright + upright	minims	lower curve + minim	limbs + inverted arch
u	Suprascript v		oblique + oblique	-	-	-
u	Uppercase u		-	-	-	-
x	x		oblique + oblique	right-to-left stroke + NE branch + SW branch	lower left branch + main stroke + upper right branch	stem + upper branch + lower branch
x	Uppercase x		-	-	-	-
y	y		stem + head-stroke	-	-	-
y	Uppercase y		-	-	-	-
z	z		curve + oblique + curve	-	-	-

z	Caroline z		head-stroke + oblique + bottom-stroke	top stroke + diagonal stroke + bottom stroke	top stroke + diagonal stroke + bottom stroke	stem + headstroke + basestroke
z	Uppercase z		-	-	-	

CHARACTER TYPE: LIGATURE

<i>characters</i>	<i>allographs</i>		<i>components (essential elements)</i>
ligature e+	e+		-
ligature r+	r+		-
ligature st	st		-
ligature t+	t+		-
ligature tj	tj		-
ligature XL	XL		-

CHARACTER TYPE: NEXUS

<i>characters</i>	<i>allographs</i>		<i>components (essential elements)</i>
nexus et	et		-
nexus iT	iT		-
nexus NT	NT		-
nexus t+	t+		-
nexus tj	tj		-

CHARACTER TYPE: ABBREVIATION

<i>characters</i>	<i>allographs</i>		<i>components (essential elements)</i>
abbrev. stroke	abbrev. stroke		abbrev. stroke

ending -us/-ue	Visigothic min. -us/-ue		abbrev. sign
ending -us/-ue	Caroline -us/-ue		abbrev. sign
ending -um	Visigothic min. -um		abbrev. sign
per	Visigothic per		abbrev. sign
per	Caroline per		abbrev. sign
pre	Caroline pre	-	abbrev. sign
qui	Visigothic qui		abbrev. sign
ending -is	Visigothic -is		abbrev. sign
-er-	Caroline -er-		abbrev. sign
-ur-	Caroline -ur-		abbrev. sign
-en-	Caroline -en-		abbrev. sign
con	con		abbrev. sign
et	Caroline et (Tironian note)		abbrev. sign

CHARACTER TYPE: PUNCTUATION

<i>characters</i>	<i>allographs</i>		<i>components (essential elements)</i>
<i>.^ punctus flexus</i>	<i>.^ punctus flexus</i>		-
<i>./ punctus elevatus</i>	<i>./ punctus elevatus</i>		-
<i>; punctus versus</i>	<i>; punctus versus</i>		-
<i>::</i>	<i>::</i>		-
<i>distinctio</i>	<i>distinctio/ media/sub</i>		-

Component features

<i>components</i>		<i>features</i>
abbrev. stroke	abbrev. stroke	with dot, without dot, angular, curved up, curved down, straight, wavy, forked
abbrev. sign	abbrev. sign	s-like vertical, s-like horizontal, semicircle, oblique, G-clef, curve, crossing descender, virgule, inverted c, 7-like
arch	h, m, n	angular, rounded, ended curved to the right, ended curved to the left, ended straight
bottom-stroke	Round r, cursive t, Caroline z	convex, concave, horizontal, turned up, wavy
bow/lobe	Caroline a, b, d, Uncial d, e, e caudata, Caroline g, k, o, p	rounded, oval, narrow, teardrop-shaped, angular
cross-stroke	e, e caudata, Open e, f, k	concave, convex, horizontal, turned up, wavy
curve	Visigothic a, c, e, e caudata, Open e, Visigothic g, q, t, Inverted beta t, Caroline t, z	c-shaped, flat-bottom, flat-top
down-stroke	Visigothic g, Caroline g, Long i, q	straight, ended curved to the right, ended curved to the left
head-stroke	c, f, Visigothic g, Long i, q, r, s, t, Caroline t, y, Caroline z	concave, convex, horizontal, turned up, wavy
oblique	x, z, cursive t, Suprascript v, Caroline z	oblique to the right, oblique to the left
stem	Caroline a, b, d, Uncial d, f, h, k, m, n, p, Inverted beta t, y	with approach stroke clubbed, wedged, forked, curved, unadorned; serif ended curved to the right, to the left, straight; diagonal, straight
upright/minim	Visigothic a, i, Tall i, l, r, Round r, s, Caroline t, u	with approach stroke clubbed, wedged, forked, curved, unadorned; serif ended curved to the right, to the left, straight
virgule	e caudata	zigzag, s-like, curly

A similar basic terminology will need to be described and tested to expand VisigothicPal to the study of the other typological variants used in Visigothic script (namely, cursive Visigothic script and elongata) particularly frequent in charters.